

Knowledge Workers In Universities

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to review research related to labor quality, knowledge in universities, labor quality of staff is knowledge in universities. Since then, the author researches research gaps and proposes future research models to evaluate the quality and productivity of the knowledge team in universities in Vietnam.

Keywords: Knowledge labor, university, labor productivity

1. Introduction

Entering the twenty-first century, the strong development of the knowledge economy and the scientific-technological revolution have not only determined the position of people at the forefront of the production force but also increasingly shaped. The role of intellectual resources is especially important in the development of internal resources of each nation and nation.

Vietnam is at a crossroads of development with accelerated industrialization and modernization. The context of the world and the era is opening up favorable prospects and conditions for Vietnam, at the same time placing our country in the face of many dangers and challenges in the integration process, in which, backwardness, Intellectual lag is the most terrifying thing.

As a cradle for training high-quality human resources, higher education Vietnam has a great responsibility in the process of creating and developing intellectual potentials for the nation. This explains why now, overcoming the bottleneck of highly qualified human resources through the improvement of the labor quality of the higher education intelligentsia is posed as a strategic solution for development. Ethnic mania that Vietnam must pay great attention to. It is a direct result of the increase in intellectual resources that Vietnam as well as other countries pay special attention to in the face of competitiveness in an economy based on the strength of knowledge, science and technology.

This important issue is also explained from the long-standing weaknesses that have been slowly overcome in the quality of human resource training of higher education in our country. The deeper the integration into integration, the more the quality of human resource training in Vietnam is influenced by the laws of competition and the negative impacts of the market mechanism. Worrying is the inadequacy of the qualifications, capacities and manifestations of individualism, pragmatism, formal labor, lack of conscientiousness and dedication of many educators and intellectuals before the responsibility of glory of the "cultivating" career. Especially the challenges posed from the quality of the human resources trained at university have not yet met the requirements of the domestic and international labor markets. That is alien to the nature of creative scientific pedagogical labor and noble quality of teachers, if not promptly overcome, it will certainly leave "sequelae" for human resources that not only exist in reality now but also in the future.

To overcome these obstacles and challenges, it is necessary to have synchronous solutions, especially breakthrough solutions to improve the stated current situation. It is the need to find the key to the development of human resources that has made the labor quality issue of higher education intellectuals a constant and top concern of leaders, managers as well as the whole. society in the process of implementing the educational revolution. On the other hand, it is also a condition to ensure the existence and sustainable development of Vietnamese higher education institutions in the context of competition, international integration, and social expectations in innovation. From educational subjects, from higher education programs and methods, the highest purpose is to improve the quality of trained human resources. This is an urgent requirement of the society. It is a difficult, complicated work that costs a lot of effort, time, energy, mind and money.

On a higher level, belonging to responsibility, social conscience, paying attention to the labor quality of higher education intellectuals is taking care of the nation's intellectual resource training. In order to ensure the reliability of the country's development and sustainable strategy, it is necessary to find a breakthrough from human potentials on the material support of economic development. The basis for creating intellectual resources cannot be outside higher education but the key is in the labor quality of the contingent of intellectuals of teachers.

Only with such a dialectical look can we see the importance and the urgency of why it is necessary to innovate higher education, starting from the changes in the labor quality of the management staff as well as generations of teachers. University. Interpreting and surveying this issue to find solutions to development that not only make sense but also contribute to the implementation of the policy of quality accreditation of universities according to the standard system of the Ministry of Education and Training to " fundamentally and comprehensively renovating the education system "according to the spirit of the Party's Central Resolution 8, Session XI.

The objective of the article is to review research works related to the labor quality of the knowledge team in universities, from which to propose future research directions.

2. Literature review

2.1. Typical research works directly discussing intellectuals

Firstly, the typical research works have been printed into books:

- Prof, Dr. Pham Tat Dong (editor): "The development orientation of the contingent of Vietnamese intellectuals in industrialization and modernization" [42]. The work has relevant explanations on the role of intellectuals in developing production forces, in cultural creation, promoting national identity, in leadership, management and administration of industrialization and modernization. country. With an attitude of respect for intellectuals, Professor, Dr. Pham Tat Dong affirmed, in the market economy, "the labor product of intellectuals is a special commodity, it can be lost or appropriated. No one knows, but it can also be circulated and paid the price worthy of many other rare goods "[42, p.330]. This is the source of the innovation of thinking when considering salary and allowances of intellectuals as the most beneficial investment policies to buy back "brain matter" - a special product in the economy. market.

- Dr. Nguyen Dac Hung: "Vietnamese intellectuals before the requirement of developing the country" [72] and "Vietnamese intellectuals advance at the same time" [73]. Two books clarify the concept of intellectuals; position and role of intellectuals; the main directions to build and develop the contingent of intellectuals in our country to meet the requirements of the times. On the basis of asserting the very broad connotation of the concept of intellectuals, the author has pointed out: intellectuals are people who not only have a high level of education, but the most important thing is that they actually work with intellectual creativity, there are certain contributions that are useful to the society and must be assessed by the society through practical activities [72, pp.16-17]. This is the renewal of intellectual thinking, from attaching importance to the trained expertise to recognizing and requiring actual labor capacity through the objective social examination.

- Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen An Ninh: "Promoting the potential of intellectuals, social sciences and humanities in national renewal" [109]. From the explanations about the potential of social science and humanities intellectuals in the current period, the author has proposed practical solutions to promote the potential of this team to contribute to promoting industrialization and modernization of the land. country.

- Prof., Dr. Nguyen Van Khanh - Editor of two works: "Building and promoting Vietnam's intellectual resources to serve the cause of national revival" [74]; "Vietnam's intellectual resources - History, current status and prospects" [75]. The value of the two research projects focused on scientific arguments on intellectual resources, intellectual resources with interdisciplinary approach. The contingent of intellectuals is conceived by the author as the elite class of Vietnam's intellectual resources. On the basis of surveying and evaluating the quality of this human resource, the author has proposed a system of solutions that have practical significance for building and promoting the role of intellectual resources to meet the requirements, the requirements of the country revival career.

- Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen Khanh Turn, M. Tran Thi Huyen (co-editor), "Building a contingent of intellectuals in the period of accelerating industrialization and modernization according to Ho Chi Minh ideology" [18]. This is an in-depth research on intellectuals from the perspective of Ho Chi Minh's thought. The author has outlined the basic contents of Ho Chi Minh's thought on intellectuals, clarified the creative application of the Party and the State in the work of intellectual building, and evaluated the contributions and limitations. of this team in the Vietnamese revolution, on that basis, deeply analyzed solutions to build a contingent of intellectuals in our country in the period 2011-2020 to meet the requirements of the cause of the country's industrialization and modernization.

Second, scientific researches on intellectuals:

- Prof., Dr. Pham Tat Dong with State-level scientific topics, code KX 04 - 06: "Scientific arguments for policies to promote the creative capacity of intellectuals and students" [40] has focused on analyzing and clarifying the theoretical, practical and legal basis of policy making, solutions aimed at arousing, exploiting and using the creative capacity of intellectuals and students in activities. education and training activities.

- Associate Professor, Dr. Dam Duc Vuong, Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen Viet Thong: "Building a contingent of Vietnamese intellectuals in the period of 2011-2020" [161]. This is an elaborate and systematic study of intellectuals. On the basis of the overall assessment of the current state of Vietnam's intellectuals, the topic analyzes in-depth and recommends solutions to build up and promote intellectual resources in the period of comprehensive national renewal. The topic has clarified the connotation of the concept of intellectuals on a large scale. Not only pointing out the nature of intellectual labor along with the requirements for understanding, qualifications, aspirations for democracy, justice, freedom and creative results in the dissemination, dissemination and application of life. Social life of intellectuals, the authors of the topic also clearly define the natural position, quality and character of Vietnamese intellectuals.

Third, studies on intellectuals have successfully protected in recent years:

- Associate Professor, Dr. Phan Thanh Khoi: "The driving force of intellectuals in creative work in our country today" [77]. On the basis of identifying the intellectual force as "special social class", the author explains the working nature of the intellectuals while also focusing on clarifying the creative labor dynamics and solutions. France mainly promotes the role of the contingent of intellectuals in our country today.

- Associate Professor, Dr. Do Thi Thach: "Vietnamese female intellectuals in the current renovation - the potential and direction of construction" [133]. This is an in-depth study of the female intellectual force. The author has made new contributions in both theory and practice in explaining the potential as well as the great role of the Vietnamese female intellectual force in the development of social life. Stemming from the attitude of respect and trust in this force's ability to contribute, the author has proposed basic directions to promote the potential and role of female intellectuals in the cause of the national revolution. Vietnam, especially in the comprehensive renovation process of the country.

- Dr. Nguyen Cong Tri: "Vietnamese intellectuals in the development of knowledge economy" [146]. From the integrated approach, the research shows the basic characteristics and criteria to determine the intellectuals, the role of this team in the conditions of knowledge economy development. Research has determined that intellectuals are intellectual workers and often have high levels of education, training or self-training. However, "the most important values of a true intellectual are truth and truth; intellectual is a person who is confident and upright, has self-esteem, is able to behave properly and is highly adaptable to the changes of the natural and social environment "[146, p.30].

Fourth, the typical studies on intellectuals have been published in journals in recent years:

Entering the stage of promoting industrialization and modernization of the country, the request for renewed thinking on intellectual issues has been raised in the concern of many scientists. Continuing to clarify the scientific and revolutionary nature of Marxism-Leninism and the correct understanding of our Party in the view of intellectuals is an important theoretical research direction. Some articles published in magazines in recent years have mentioned this issue, typically: "The team of intellectuals in the industrialization and modernization of the country" by Associate Professor, Dr. Phan Thanh Khoi. [78]; "Lessons from Lenin's point of view on intellectuals" by Associate Professor, Dr. Phan Thanh Khoi [79]; "Ponder and awareness about intellectual issues", Journal of Political Theory, 2008, No. 9 of Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen Duc Bach [17].

In addition, it should be emphasized that, in recent years, on the rise in both quantity and quality of Vietnamese intellectuals, new aspects of functions, tasks, recruitment policies, remuneration, solutions to promote the role of intellectuals in order to meet the requirements and requirements of the process of industrialization, modernization, integration, and development of knowledge economy have also been set out and seriously studied. There are a number of articles of scientific value such as: "Some issues need innovation to create motivation and conditions for our country's intellectuals to promote their intellectual talents" by Nguyen Duc Bach [16]; "Overview of our current intellectual contingent" [81] and "Scientist and creativity in social sciences" [82] by Associate Professor, Dr. Phan Thanh Khoi.

The above-mentioned research works have provided important theoretical and practical basis for the author to argue about intellectuals, on the role of intellectuals in the conditions of innovation, integration and development of intellectual economy. knowledge and industrialization and modernization of the country.

2.2. The research works on higher education intellectuals, the characteristics and labor quality of higher education intellectuals

Firstly, the general studies on higher education intellectuals:

Through clarifying concepts, positions, roles, functions, and duties of teachers; surveying the current status of the structure and quality of higher education intellectuals, many research projects have proposed solutions to build and develop this contingent at the university level. These typical projects can be mentioned as follows:

- Dr. Pham Van Thanh: "Building a contingent of Marxist-Leninist scientific intellectuals in universities in our country today" [131]. The author clearly states that the teaching team of Marxist-Leninist theory in Vietnam is both educators, scientists and politicians. The role of that team is mentioned and analyzed by the author in many aspects from the function of staff training, developing a new intellectual force for the country to undertaking scientific research and participating in other work. in the system of universities and colleges under the national education system. On the basis of evaluating the status and changing trends of the Marxist-Leninist scientific team in our country, the author has proposed major solutions to build this team into a strong, contributing force. more and more wisdom for the cause of building socialism in Vietnam today.

- Dr. Do Minh Cuong - Nguyen Thi Doan "Developing human resources for higher education in Vietnam" [38]. With the view that university teachers are the most important and decisive factor to the quality of human resource training in our country, the author has deeply analyzed the role of higher education intellectuals, thereby proving. a number of solutions to build and develop human resources for higher education before the requirements of international integration.

- Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen Van Son: "Vietnamese Higher Education Intellectuals in the period of accelerating industrialization and modernization" [126]. According to the author, the contingent of Vietnamese higher education intellectuals has a number of basic characteristics: the force directly participating in the training process at the highest level in the national education system; subjects mainly affected by higher education intellectuals are students, graduate students and graduate students; labor purpose is to train creative workers with good ethical qualities; Higher education intellectuals are both teachers and scientists, politicians. From assessing the current status of the structure and quality of higher education intellectuals, the author gives the basic directions and solutions to develop the contingent of higher education intellectuals to meet the requirements of human resources serving the industrialization process. , The country OS.

- The Ministry of Education and Training: "Renovating the higher education system in the period 2010 - 2012" [26]. The study has introduced the Resolution of the Party Committee of the Ministry of Education and Training on higher education management innovation in the period 2010 - 2012. The Resolution has seriously pointed out the limitation in the quality of higher education and affirms the need necessary to promote the evaluation and accreditation of higher education quality; formed in higher education institutions to organize a specialized organization in guiding, protecting and exploiting intellectual property of lecturers; honor and create better and better conditions for teachers at university level to promote their activeness in scientific research. It can be affirmed that this is an important legal basis that has the meaning of guiding the research author in building solutions to improve the labor quality of Vietnamese higher education intellectuals today.

Starting from the viewpoint that higher education intellectuals are the most decisive factor to the quality of human resource training, many researchers have focused on explaining the position and role of higher education intellectuals at the same time finding a system of solutions. fundamentally creating labor motivation for the contingent of university educators. Regarding that problem, in recent years, there have been a number of scientific works, notably:

- Associate Professor, Dr. Bui Khac Viet (Chair): "Young intellectuals and students" [160]. The author has directly affirmed the role of young intellectuals and students in universities and colleges. On the basis of evaluating achievements, limitations and shortcomings, especially the quality of that force before the requirements and requirements of socio-economic development practice, the author comes to affirm the team development. Young intellectuals and students in universities and colleges are essential jobs.

- In addition to the above works, there are a number of research papers published by scholars on journals and conference proceedings, such as: Nguyen Van Due: "University teaching staff - reality status and recommendations" [43]; Nguyen Duy Yen: "Renovating education must firstly innovate from educators" [176]; Dinh Thi Minh Tuyet: "Building and developing university faculty" [153]. In general, the above authors have the same opinion when considering teachers at university level as the core force building for students' worldview, progressive humanism, knowledge equipment and thinking methods. science, ability to work independently and creatively for learners. In order to improve the quality of teachers, the authors said, it is necessary to focus on renovating the training and fostering of teachers in the direction of standardization and modernization; The arrangement and use of teachers must be reasonable, respect true creative capacity in professional expertise and at the same time create a motivational system for the contingent of teachers.

Secondly, the initial studies directly discuss the labor characteristics of higher education intellectuals:

- The author Do Van Phuc with the article "The labor characteristics of university and vocational teachers" [117] mainly emphasizes the characteristics of the working nature and the professional characteristics of higher education intellectuals. The author's assessment, the labor of the faculty is a creative type, intellectual labor, with some harmful factors and specific stresses.

- Determining the labor nature of higher education intellectuals, Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen Thi My Loc and Dr. Dang Xuan Hai with the subject "University teachers and pedagogical communication", "Teaching methods at the university level "In the fostering document" Higher Education "has given the concept:" In university, the pedagogical creativity goes hand in hand with the scientific creation "[53, p.217]. Therefore, university teaching activities are carried out by those who are attached to scientific research. In addition to the qualifications and competencies of experts, they must have two competency qualities that are most significant to professional workers, pedagogical and scientific research competencies. Training the skills of an enthusiastic scientist and pedagogy is an indispensable requirement to improve the professional quality of university lecturers.

- Associate Professor, Dr. Pham Hong Quang - author of the book "Educational environment" [119] gives the conception of labor characteristics of higher education intellectuals. The author affirms that, the object of pedagogical work is the developing student character; To influence this object, the teacher needs to use the tools as his or her own personality; Pedagogical labor function is reproduction of social labor force; the labors' labor is professional intellectual labor; it requires of the instructors science, art and creativity. The author said that the pedagogical labor characteristics also stipulate the basic requirements on the personality of the teacher, so the educator must have pedagogical capacity and the combination of professional ethical qualities such as: worldview science, ideal for training the young generation and love for people, love the profession.

- When explaining "The nature of creative activities in scientific research" [9], Professor, Dr. Hoang Chi Bao emphasized: Higher education associates teaching with scientific research and serving production. The contingent of teachers and scientists have regular and long-term cooperation and relationship with each other. Their form of labor has many essential similarities. It is the discovery, the creation of new values through innovations, exploring new teaching approaches and methods. Therefore, the labor of higher education intellectuals clearly shows its creativity with its rich, diverse and complex expressions.

- Dr. Nguyen Ba Can: "Completing the current policy for higher education development in Vietnam" [31]. Approaching features of higher education in market economic conditions, the author said that as a service

product, higher education has full economic properties like other products, goods and services, but it is not suitable for buying or selling goods. When compared with other types of services, "higher education products and services also have a specificity - that is, citizens who are useful to themselves, responsible to the family, society and the country. Such products are called goods with a forward margin "[31, p.22].

- Dr. Ngo Van Ha: "Ho Chi Minh's thought about teachers and the construction of the current university faculty" [66]. On the basis of analyzing the contents of Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on teachers, the author has raised a number of dissertations on the labor characteristics of lecturers: teaching is a specific type of labor; "A university teacher must incorporate within himself the qualities of a scientist and an educator - teaching; Their task is not only to train highly qualified human resources for the country, but also to provide scientific support for research institutes and business and production establishments "[66, p.158]. The instructors' revolutionary morality is their passion for teaching, research, honesty in science, creative exploration, and the desire to conquer the pinnacle of knowledge.

Third, the research works initially mentioning the labor quality of higher education intellectuals:

- In 2006, Prof., Dr. Nguyen Duc Chinh and Associate Professor, Dr. Nguyen Phuong Nga accepted the topic "Research to develop evaluation criteria for university teaching and scientific research activities of lecturers in the National University" [37]. The practical value of the topic is shown in the renewal recommendations of the teaching and scientific research evaluation criteria of the lecturers, taking into account the global integration trend in higher education. This is a study on the field of measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of the responsibilities and tasks of the teaching staff carried out by experts and educational administrators, so the research results have important implications in the suggesting the approach towards overall assessment of the labor quality of higher education intellectuals for the study author.

- In 2008, the World Bank's East Asia and Pacific Human Development Division published the Report "Higher Education and Skills for Growth" [113]. The report focuses on higher education in relation to the labor market in Vietnam. Many important contents about the quality of higher education have been explained, surveyed and proven. Noteworthy is the issue of training effectiveness; curriculum, pedagogical methods; quality of teaching staff; research capacity of lecturers; student satisfaction; ability, the level of adequate provision of the necessary skills of higher education in Vietnam for human resources, for increasing labor productivity and promoting the creative capacity of employees in the face of increasingly demanding requirements. high from domestic, regional and international markets. The research results of the Report have important implications for the research author in inheriting the data proving the effectiveness of teaching and scientific research of the contingent of higher education intellectuals.

- In 2010, the PhD thesis: "Evaluating university lecturers in the direction of standardization in the current period" by Tran Xuan Bach [15] was successfully defended. In the aspect of educational management, the author can inherit and absorb the results of the research on a number of aspects such as perceptions of university lecturers, the theoretical basis of the methods of teacher evaluation. . The author has identified and evaluated lecturers as the process of comprehensively describing, collecting, processing and analyzing the system of information about the trainers, and then judging the true value of their labor. .

- Associate Professor, Dr. Tran Quoc Toan (editor): "Developing education in the context of market economy and international integration" [145]. The outstanding value of the research is the scientific arguments about the relationship between education - training and the market in both theoretical and practical aspects, especially surveys, assessments and arguments. award on the quality of human resources, the response of education and training in general, higher education in particular to the social needs of the impact of the market economy and the international integration process.

There are also many independent articles of scientists researching on the quality of higher education in general, the quality of the labor force of lecturers in particular, typically:

- Nguyen Duc Chinh, Nguyen Phuong Nga: "Research to develop a set of criteria for evaluating the quality of university training" [35]. The article has identified the criteria for evaluating the professional quality of higher education intellectuals, in which special attention should be paid to signs of the ability and level of satisfaction, to meet the job requirements of teachers' intellectuals. .

- Phan Van Kha: "Applying ISO 9000 quality management model in postgraduate training management in Vietnam". The article is presented in the book "Educational development strategy in the twenty-first century - experiences of nations" [76]. Through studying different conceptions of quality in the fields, the author has given the concept that the quality of higher education is the satisfaction of customers' needs and is assessed by the degree of coincidence with the target. predefined.

- Approaching and reflecting the quality of higher education can also be mentioned the article "Quality assurance system in universities according to the point of view of Southeast Asian university network" by Ta Thi Thu Hien. [70]. The author directly discusses the evaluation process, the training quality accreditation criteria of universities, in which emphasis on the fields of professional teaching, scientific research, training management of lecturers, quality of inputs - students and output factor quality - trained human resources.

- Le Huu Ai, Lam Ba Hoa: "Higher education in Vietnam today - Current situation and solutions to improve quality" [3]. In the article, the two authors have focused on analyzing the shortcomings and weaknesses of higher education in our country today, especially the quality aspect of human resource training. On that basis, the article demonstrates a number of solutions to enhance the role of higher education in economic development in our country today.

- Pham Ngoc Trung: "The quality of education in universities in our country today" [147]. With the concept, the quality of higher education is "the whole system of professional qualifications, ethical qualities, integration ability and stable employment of students upon graduation" [147, p.38], the author have analyzed the factors affecting the quality of education in universities in our country today, that is the contingent of teachers, learners, technical facilities and management.

2.3. Overseas research works related to the study

In the past, the intellectual issue has naturally become an important research object of many scientists. Various aspects of this problem such as: intellectual concept; positions, roles, functions, duties of intellectuals; The reality of quantity, structure, quality and a series of issues of direction and solutions to develop intellectual contingent has been explained at many levels, typically:

- Tham Vinh Hoa - Ngo Quoc Dieu (editor): "Respect for intellectuals, respect for the great talent for hundreds of years of reviving the country" translated by Nguyen Nhu Diem [71]. This work has mentioned many important contents in Deng Xiaoping's thought about intellectuals. Deng Xiaoping's meaningful and guiding views on talent issues, the way of organizing, building and developing the contingent of intellectuals, especially thoughts on the work of fostering, training and using and treatment of talents carefully interpreted by authors Tham Vinh Hoa and Ngo Quoc Dieu. Since then, the book also initially clarifies the application of Deng Xiaoping's thought in the strategy of building talent and developing the contingent of intellectuals in China over the years.

In most countries, higher education intellectuals are highly valued by the state. Therefore, many research subjects often find the need to pay attention to teachers' intellectuals, especially the teaching staff.

- J.Vial - French educator, in the book "History and Current events on pedagogical methods" [156] has created a new perspective on the working characteristics of the educators at university level. J.Vial asserted: Teachers not only do well their dual function, they know how to convey what learners need, but also know how to organize the cognitive process for learners to actively and actively dominate the learning content. . To perform the role of "referee, advisor" in the teaching process, a teacher must have the qualities of a teacher and a scientist at the same time. From J.Vial's argument, it can be seen as specific characteristics of labor in terms of functions and professional tasks of higher education intellectuals.

- J.A Centra with typical studies such as: "Self-assessment of university lecturers: A comparison with students' assessment" [32]; Determine the effectiveness of teachers' work [33]. J.A Centra said that any lecturer needs to fully perform key functions and tasks such as teaching, scientific research, professional services for the community. Therefore, it is necessary to focus on assessing the quality or effectiveness of the work of university teachers according to the three main areas of activity mentioned.

- Ph.N.Gônôlin: "The psychological qualities of the teacher" [65]. When discussing the specificity of teaching work, the author said that two basic aspects in pedagogical activities are "teaching and education.

These two aspects of pedagogical activity are closely related, penetrate together and are a unified process. What is emphasized by the author is the change in the teacher's role and duties in the new era associated with the explosion of knowledge: "Teachers are not truth-communicators but leaders and organizations. skillful work of students in class "[65, p.76]. To meet that transformation, each teacher himself must promote the active teaching as an important attribute. Identifying the psychological qualities of the teacher, the author paid special attention to signs of creative ability. It is a common feature of pedagogical labor that without it, teaching merely imparts one-way knowledge, it is easy to fall into stereotypes, mechanics and boredom.

- Franz Emanuel Weinert in his work "Cognitive development of learning and teaching" [164] focused on explaining the characteristics of active teachers. An important content in Franz Emanuel Weinert's work is the determination of the criteria of a teacher intellectual with good professional activities. According to the author, it is the person who "exhibits a pedagogical act characterized by different qualities directed, controlling and supporting students according to their goals" [163, p.537]. Through his work, Franz Emanuel Weinert also mentioned the effectiveness and quality of teaching - an important aspect constituting labor of higher education intellectuals.

- UNESCO organized activities to gather human intelligence to think about an education for the twenty-first century culminating in "Higher Education in the Twenty - First Century - vision and Action" [178]. The conference adopted the Declaration on Higher Education with the determination of the core mission of the higher education system and the functions and duties of the faculty in the twenty-first century. Declaration defines, quality in higher education is a multidimensional concept, covering all its functions and activities: teaching, training programs, scientific research, faculty and students, infrastructure and the academic environment, in which the teacher's factor plays the most decisive role. The Declaration also clearly states that there should be a strong policy on team development that can improve their skills, encourage creativity, promote activeness, and proactively in research and teaching.

- J.M.Denomme and Medeleine Roy with the book "Towards an interactive pedagogy" [39]. The two authors said that, in the teaching process, active pedagogical methods are considered as all of the teacher's interventions with the aim of helping learners perform the process of acquiring knowledge or skills, from which to learn. how to search and process information, creating their respective capacities. This affirmation shows that learners are both the object and the working goal of the teacher; Labor results of higher education intellectuals in teaching activities must be manifested in the formation of students 'self-study and self-study methods under the guidance of teachers' intellectuals.

Synthesis of the above studies has identified a new perspective on the labor of university educators. Accordingly, the quality of higher education is also envisioned as a multidimensional concept covering all functions and activities of the school.

3. Conclusion

It can be said that a rich amount of knowledge with many elaborate studies on intellectuals shows the attractiveness or special importance of this issue for the development of society. The scientific value of a large amount of documents, theoretical and practical researches on intellectuals, higher education intellectuals has created favorable conditions for research on the labor quality of the contingent of higher education intellectuals in the country. me now.

From the overview of the research related to the research, the author would give the following general assessment:

Firstly, the studies have outlined a system of intellectual approaches and the contingent of higher education intellectuals. It is noteworthy that the views that view intellectuals as a social force, a socio-occupational group are identified and delineated by their intellectually laborious, creative and complex mode and nature. In recent years, the research works on the conception of intellectuals often focus on the criteria of responsibility and efficiency to contribute to the social development from the specific professional activities of each intellectual subject. in the career structure. This is the addition of a new approach to knowledge, it is conceived and gradually becomes a central research direction in the process of renewing thinking, especially in the context of the development of knowledge economy.

Secondly, the theoretical studies on intellectuals, educational intellectuals, higher education intellectuals are quite plentiful, but research on the labor quality of intellectuals, higher educated intellectuals is still few. There are no state-level monograph studies or scientific research projects and programs, nor has there been any research that directly systematically elaborates on this issue.

Third, under different angles, aspects and scope of research, the research related research has solved a number of theoretical and practical problems about higher education intellectuals. To a certain extent, the labor characteristics of the faculty are mentioned. However, the published works have not exploited the problem in depth from the perspective of the relationship between the full perception of labor characteristics and the establishment of the criteria to evaluate the quality of labor of the intellectual staff. Knowledge higher education in Vietnam. In the context of globalization, integration, competition, innovation and the development of the knowledge economy, it is an issue closely related to the current strategy of human resource development in our country, but not yet directly. deep research, evaluation, review and find solutions for development. Moreover, the theoretical research on the labor characteristics of the new higher education intellectuals is mentioned in a limited level or in each specific aspect, mainly discussing the responsibilities, duties, objects and working tools. Labor and labor nature of lecturers and scientists.

Fourthly, in terms of the labor quality of higher education intellectuals, the published researches mainly approach general aspects of professional qualifications, profession, political qualities, ideology, ethics. or just focus on evaluating the duties of teachers in terms of approaching education. The method of evaluating the quality of lecturers was initially interested and explained, however, the authors still have little detail on specifying the evaluation method through quantitative criteria. In fact, the theory about the labor quality of higher education intellectuals has not been studied in a comprehensive, systematic perspective with the perspective of the interdisciplinary approach of philosophy - politics - society - education.

Fifth, many practical aspects of improving the labor quality of the contingent of higher education intellectuals have not been clarified such as: the current situation, the problems posed from the current situation; the regulation of the labor quality of the contingent of teachers at tertiary training institutions nationwide; mechanism, level and effectiveness of the impact of guidelines, policies and laws on the improvement of the labor quality of the contingent of higher education intellectuals in our country today.

Sixthly, the clarification of the labor quality of the contingent of intellectuals managing higher education in Vietnam is still a new issue, there are no in-depth studies towards theoretical and general construction. The practical results of the labor quality of this team meet the requirements of renovating the management system of higher education in Vietnam in the current period.

Seventhly, there are many unproven problems that in this study, on the basis of absorbing the results of previous research projects, will focus on solving such as:

- Through the exploitation and inheritance of research results from relevant domestic and foreign scientific works, with the interdisciplinary approach of philosophy - politics - society - education, formative research. the new systematic concept of the labor quality of higher education intellectuals and the specificity of the current Vietnamese higher education intellectual labor.

- Building up a scientific foundation for the inevitability of improving the labor quality of Vietnamese higher education intellectuals in the current context.

- Research to establish the criteria for evaluating the labor quality of higher education intellectuals as a scientific basis for surveying the labor quality situation of the contingent of Vietnamese higher education intellectuals in public universities.

- Researching to clarify some problems posed to the labor quality of the current Vietnamese higher education contingent, thereby proposing solutions related to innovation and leadership enhancement. of the Party, the managerial role of the State; awareness education; to train and foster to raise the pedagogical qualifications and capacities and ethical qualities of the contingent of lecturers and training administrators at universities; reforming motivational mechanisms and policies; strengthen labor quality accreditation work of the contingent of higher education intellectuals in Vietnam today.

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